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Gender norms and parents' employment characteristics in Europe

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European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: Gender norms and parents' employment characteristics in Europe

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Introduction

In 2023, 79.7% of women aged 25 to 54 without children were employed in the European Union, a rate 4.8 percentage points higher than that of women with children, whose employment rate stood at 74.9%. Although this gap has narrowed over the past two decades, it remains significant. Conversely, the impact of parenthood on men's employment is the opposite. In 2023, 91.9% of men in the same age group with children were employed, compared to 83.7% of men without children. Differences by gender and parental status are also important for other labour market features — see Figure 1. For example, women are much more likely to work in a part-time basis than men, particularly mothers. Self-employment is more common among men than among women, with fathers being the most likely to establish themselves in such type of employment. Mothers are the most likely to work from home whereas fathers are the least likely.

Figure 1: Job characteristics by gender and household composition in the European Union, 2009–2023

Note: Adults with and without children aged 25 to 54 in the EU-27.

Source: Own elaboration, using data from the EU-LFS.

This paper aims to provide new knowledge about the extent to which gender norms among fathers and mothers shape not only the likelihood of being employed (Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas, 2021) but also the type of job characteristics that parents hold in Europe. We hypothesize that gender norms progressivity could be influencing multiple decisions in the labour market as working part-time, being self-employed, doing remote work or establishing oneself in the public sector, among others. This is an aspect that has been completely overlooked by previous literature. For example, Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas (2021), our main reference in this paper, investigate the influence of gender norms on the employment gap of mothers, finding a positive association between progressive beliefs held by previous cohorts and mothers' probability of working while having a small child (relative to similar childless women and to similar fathers). However, in their case, they solely consider the likelihood for parents of being employed and ignore other characteristics of employment that may also be shaped by gender norms. Yet a better understanding of the link between gender norms and employment characteristics is necessary if we are to design effective policies that help reduce inequalities in the labour market and provide mothers and fathers a better balance between their working life and their care responsibilities.

This paper uses data at the individual level from the European Union – Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) to build a database that contains information on the likelihood of being employed as well as multiple job characteristics. It considers the variables on household structure to be able to compare the situation of parents from that of childless adults. This database is merged with data from the Integrated Values Survey (which encompasses the European Value Study and the World Value Survey) on gender norms from previous cohorts. This is an important aspect of our analysis: in order to avoid problems of endogeneity and reverse causality between labour market decisions and gender norms, we consider the gender norms of previous generations and assume that conservative and progressive beliefs are transmitted from generation to generation — a fact that has already been shown by previous literature (Farré and Vella, 2013). Our results are then drawn from an instrumental variable (IV) approach by which our potentially endogenous variable (gender norms) is instrumented by the prevalence of highly religious individuals in previous generations, in a given year, and in a given region which we show has a strong negative link with progressive beliefs.

Our main results document that the interrelationship between gender norms and labour market attachment and job characteristics is more relevant for fathers than it is for mothers. This way, living in a region where previous generations held more progressive beliefs is negatively associated with the likelihood of being employed for fathers (compared to childless men) while for mothers the coefficient is not statistically different from zero (at 95%).¹ There is the possibility that more progressive fathers take on more care responsibilities and therefore are less likely to be employed. Gender norms influence only two of the 10 job characteristics analysed in the case of mothers: part-time and remote work. The more progressive previous generations are, the more likely mothers are to work on a part-time basis and telework regularly — therefore making more use of two features that provide flexibility in the labour market. The interrelationship between gender norms and job characteristics is stronger among fathers with

¹ These results contrast those of Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas (2021) who provide evidence of a positive link between progressive gender norms and the likelihood of being employed among mothers. In the case of fathers, a negative interrelationship is also found by the authors as we do; however, their estimates do not attain statistical significance. However, their analysis could be underpowered given that it is based on a sample of around 16,000 observations compared with more than 4,000,000 used in this study.

seven out of 10 job characteristics being influenced by the progressivity of gender norms (at 95%) — positively for being a supervisor, teleworking and having a high-skill job; and, negatively for working part-time, having multiple jobs, being underemployed and in the public sector. In this respect, we find that progressive gender norms influence the likelihood among fathers of holding a more advantageous job.

This paper contributes to three strands of literature. First, we enrich previous studies on fatherhood and (mostly) motherhood penalties, which examine the persistent negative impact of children on labour market outcomes (particularly for women). While most of this literature has focused on employment gaps, wage differentials, and career interruptions experienced by mothers relative to childless women or fathers, our paper adds to this body of work by examining how parenthood affects the type of employment parents engage in and the extent to which it is shaped by social norms. By considering a broader set of outcomes, we offer a more nuanced view of how the parenthood penalty manifests in the structure and quality of parents' employment.

Second, we contribute to the literature that examines the effect of gender norms on labour market decisions (Fortin, 2005; Fernandez and Fogli, 2009; Nicoletti et al., 2018; Bursztyrn et al., 2020; Cavapozzi et al., 2021; Boneva et al., 2022; Hermes et al., 2024; Boelmann et al., 2025). While previous research has primarily focused on the binary decision of whether or not to work, this paper expands the scope by analysing how women and men participate in the labour market after becoming parents. We explore how prevailing social norms about gender roles influence decisions across various dimensions of work, including flexibility, autonomy, and authority. By doing so, we provide a deeper understanding of how cultural expectations and social constraints shape not only women's labour supply decisions but also men's. Furthermore, and compared to the previous analysis from Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas (2021), we also cover a longer period of time, more European regions and can make use of a much larger sample.

Third, this paper contributes methodologically to the literature by employing an instrumental variable approach to identify the causal effect of gender norms on labour market outcomes. We use the regional share of highly religious individuals as an instrument for gender norms in order to deal with the endogeneity concerns inherent in measuring culture — particularly that norms may both influence and be shaped by labour market behaviour. This strategy leverages the association between religiosity and traditional gender role attitudes, while addressing concerns that observed gender norms may be endogenous to local economic conditions. By doing so, we strengthen the causal interpretation of our findings and provide more robust evidence on the role of culture in shaping maternal employment patterns and occupational outcomes.

This paper is structured as follows. After this introduction, Section 2 provides a literature review on the interrelationship between gender norms and employment characteristics by gender. Section 3 details the multiple datasets we use in this study. Section 4 discusses the identification strategy while Section 5 presents the main results as well as all the robustness checks. Section 6 concludes.

2. Literature review

The evolution of gender norms has long shaped men's and women's engagement in the labour market, influencing not only whether they work but also how they work, in what roles, and for how many hours. Over the past several decades, shifting social expectations have particularly expanded women's economic opportunities. The 1960s witnessed profound shifts in young women's life aspirations. The introduction of the contraceptive pill gave women unprecedented control over reproduction, allowing them to delay marriage and childbearing and prioritize higher education and career development in their early adulthood. Moreover, rising female labour force participation inspired younger generations to pursue economic independence and professional success. These factors, combined with delayed marriages and higher divorce rates, prompted a reevaluation of the traditional norms surrounding marriage and family dynamics, emphasising women's careers and self-reliance (Goldin, 2006). As gender norms slowly became more egalitarian, women increasingly pursued work outside the home before starting families.

A large body of literature confirms that prevailing gender norms significantly affect women's labour market outcomes. In societies or communities where traditional norms emphasize women's role as homemakers, women tend to participate less in paid work and earn lower incomes. For example, in China, Chuanchuan and Jingwen (2021) find that attitudes linking women to housework are associated with lower employment rates and earnings. Similarly, in Japan, Rodríguez-Planas and Tanaka (2022) document that women holding more progressive beliefs are more likely to participate in the labour force. Uunk (2015) shows that, across European countries, women with egalitarian gender-role attitudes have a higher probability of being employed. In the Netherlands, Khoudja and Fleischmann (2014) report that women who endorse traditional gender roles not only participate less in the labour force but, when employed, work fewer hours. These findings are also present in Germany, where Tolciu and Zierahn (2012) demonstrate that not only a woman's own gender-role attitudes but also those of her partner and peers significantly shape her employment status and working hours.

While egalitarian attitudes consistently correlate with stronger labour market attachment for women, the same is not true for men. Although the literature here is more limited, several studies suggest that men's gender norms have little effect on their employment or working hours (Fortin, 2005; Corrigan and Konrad, 2007; Lietzmann and Frodermann, 2021). Men, historically seen as breadwinners, are less influenced by changing social norms, maintaining consistently high labour force participation regardless of personal beliefs. These dynamics, however, can shift once men and women enter parenthood, a life transition that often accentuates gendered expectations.

Childbirth is one of the most pivotal events in an individual's life, and it is within the context of parenthood that gender norms become especially salient. Women, anticipating the challenges of balancing work and family, make decisions about education, careers, marriage, and fertility with cultural expectations in mind (Fortin, 2005; Giuliano, 2021). Traditional norms that position women as primary caregivers and men as financial providers continue to exert influence even in today's societies. This dynamic can hinder women's access to high-paying jobs and contributes to the well-documented "motherhood penalty" in the labour market (Kleven et al., 2024).

Deviating from socially accepted gender roles can carry both social and psychological costs. People derive utility from conforming to identity norms and experience disutility when they violate them (Akerlof and Kranton, 2005, 2010; Bau and Fernandez, 2023). For women, prioritizing career over family can result in guilt or social criticism, which reduces the perceived benefits women get from engaging in the labour market. As a result, women often feel pressure

to adhere to the traditional caregiver role after motherhood, even when this comes at the expense of career advancement or earnings. Consequently, many interrupt their careers once they become mothers, complying with gender expectations despite personal and professional costs.

For men, the effects of parenthood often move in the opposite direction, one that aligns with the traditional breadwinner norm. Men with children are, on average, more likely to be employed and work longer hours than childless men (Kaufman and Uhlenberg, 2000). Societal expectations that “good fathers” are those that provide economically for their families, combined with increased financial responsibilities, often lead men to deepen their labour market engagement. Consequently, men frequently experience the so-called “fatherhood premium”, by which fathers earn higher wages than comparable non-fathers, even when controlling for experience and education (Glauber, 2008; Cooke and Fuller, 2018). This stands in contrast to the motherhood penalty, illustrating how parenthood shapes the labour market outcomes of men and women differently: fathers are encouraged to increase paid work, while mothers are expected to devote more time to unpaid care (Lundberg and Rose, 2000).

Traditional gender roles also shape employment patterns in terms of hours worked. Women frequently adjust their working hours to accommodate family and personal obligations, while men typically opt for part-time employment due to educational pursuits, training, or challenging labour market conditions (Cam, 2012; Drange and Egeland, 2014; Beham et al., 2019). Consequently, traditional gender roles often result in a higher proportion of women engaging in part-time work, whereas in more gender-egalitarian societies, where both genders are encouraged to balance family and career responsibilities, part-time employment among men is more prevalent (Bosch et al., 2010; Fahlen, 2014; Beham et al., 2019). Meanwhile, men remain dominant in top leadership positions. Countries with more women in managerial roles tend to exhibit less support for traditional gender norms in business, suggesting that the presence of female role models in management positions can foster a more gender-egalitarian perspective (Mensvoort et al., 2021).

Occupational choices are also influenced by gender norms. In many industrialized countries, girls underperform relative to boys in mathematics, contributing to the underrepresentation of women in STEM fields (Bedard and Cho, 2010). These performance gaps often reflect cultural expectations rather than ability, as in more gender-equal societies, the gender gap in Maths scores narrows or disappears (Guiso et al., 2008; Pope and Sydnor, 2010). Similarly, girls whose parents come from more gender-equal countries tend to perform better on Maths tests and express greater interest in Maths-related subjects (Nollenberger et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Planas and Nollenberger, 2018).

A recent strand of the literature highlights that it is not only actual societal attitudes but also the perception of social norms that significantly influences behaviour. Boneva et al. (2022) show that women’s intended labour supply is strongly predicted by perceived societal expectations. In Saudi Arabia, Bursztyn et al. (2020) show that many men privately support female employment but mistakenly believe their peers do not, fostering a false norm that discourages women’s work. Informational interventions can be powerful: when men are informed about actual societal support for women’s employment, they become significantly more willing to allow their wives to work. Similarly, Hermes et al. (2024) demonstrate that correcting misperceptions about societal norms can change both individuals’ attitudes and their expectations of others, particularly regarding maternal employment.

These external perceptions are reinforced by internal pressures, especially among mothers. Many women experience “mother’s guilt”, perceiving paid work as conflicting with their

parenting responsibilities (Buttrose and Adams, 2005). This sense of conflict often leads them to seek advice from peers to reduce uncertainty about the consequences of maternal employment (Fortin, 2005; Fernandez, 2013; Fogli and Veldkamp, 2011). In this context, exposure to counter-stereotypical behaviour is crucial. Observing women in non-traditional roles helps dismantle gender stereotypes through social learning (Bertrand, 2020). Women raised by working mothers are more likely to remain employed after child-birth and experience less work-family conflict (Olivetti et al., 2018; Rodríguez-Planas et al., 2022; McGinn et al., 2019). This intergenerational effect demonstrates that early-life exposure to progressive gender norms can enhance women's labour force attachment in adulthood. Supporting this, Corrigan and Konrad (2007) demonstrate the long-term impact of internalized gender role attitudes, showing that women with egalitarian views early in life are more likely to pursue careers and earn higher wages.

Peer effects further amplify these behavioural patterns. Older generations of women often serve as role models, shaping the values and decisions of younger women. Nicoletti et al. (2018) show that institutional shifts, such as greater childcare availability, can initiate changes in maternal employment, but it is peer influence that amplifies them. Cavapozzi et al. (2021) find that progressive peer norms substantially increase women's labour force participation, with half of the effect stemming from attitudinal conformity and the other half from behavioural spillovers. This peer and intergenerational transmission is further illustrated by Galassi et al. (2024), who find a strong link between mothers' and daughters' employment. Daughters of employed mothers are more likely to work as adults. Fernández et al. (2004) extend this pattern to men, showing that sons of working mothers are more likely to marry employed women, highlighting the transmission of gender attitudes across generations.

While gender attitudes are relatively stable, they are also shaped by key life events, such as parenthood. Egalitarian beliefs are also associated with a more equal division of unpaid labour (Bianchi et al., 2000; Gupta, 2006; Kan, 2008; Fahlen, 2016; McGinn et al., 2019). Yet even in progressive couples, parenthood often prompts a return to traditional roles. Galván and García-Peñalosa (2024) find that women's employment drops substantially after childbirth, even when they were the primary earners before the baby's birth. In contrast, men's labour supply is mostly unaffected if they were already the main breadwinner. However, if a new father had not been the primary earner, he tends to increase his work effort after the child's birth. This suggests that, even in progressive households, parenthood triggers a reversion to more traditional gender roles in terms of work and care distribution.

Consistent with this idea of "re-traditionalization" after parenthood, Grinza et al. (2020) find that couples who held egalitarian gender-role attitudes prior to becoming parents but ended up adopting a traditional division of labour once the baby was born, exhibited a shift toward more conservative attitudes post-childbirth. In other words, their beliefs adjusted to align with the reality they experienced, reflecting a form of cognitive or social realignment. Moreover, women in more traditional communities are especially susceptible to such changes: those who initially held progressive views tend to become more traditional after childbirth when surrounded by conservative social norms.

A small but growing number of studies directly examine how gender norms influence labour market outcomes following parenthood. Boelmann et al. (2025) show that women raised in more egalitarian cultures are more likely to be employed after childbirth. Similarly, Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas (2021) find that inherited egalitarian norms from earlier generations increase mothers' likelihood of working while raising young children. Kleven (2022) identifies gender norms as a key driver of child penalties, showing that progressive beliefs correlate with smaller labour market penalties for mothers.

The influence of gender norms extends beyond labour force participation, shaping working hours, occupational trajectories, and the timing of career interruptions. However, while most literature has focused on whether women work, little is known about the influence of gender norms on other job characteristics after becoming parents. This gap in the literature motivates the present study.

3. Data

In order to gain a deep understanding of the association between gender norms and parents' labour market outcomes, we rely on data from the EU-LFS from 2000 to 2022. The EU-LFS is the main data source in Europe regarding labour market participation, employment status, job characteristics, hours worked, employment in a second job, previous work experience, methods used to find employment, etc. Data are collected every quarter and annually among individuals aged 15 and above. The dataset also includes a wide range of demographic variables and household characteristics which allow us to control for family structure.

Given our focus on understanding the influence of gender norms on parental labour market characteristics while having a small child, we restrict our analysis to men and women with a child aged 0 to 5 years old. We will be comparing parents' behaviour with that of their childless counterparts, excluding those individuals with children older than 5 or who have children within the specified age range, but they do not cohabit with them regularly. Additionally, we restrict the analysis to native men and women between 20 and 39 years of age, as these are the most common childrearing years. We define someone as native if they were born in the same country where they are residing. The decision to focus on natives is related to how the gender norm indicator is constructed (see below).

In order to create our measure of gender norms, we use the Integrated Values Survey (IVS), constructed from merging the European Value Study (EVS) and the World Value Survey (WVS) from 2000 to 2022. The EVS is a large-scale, cross-national, and repeated cross-sectional survey which collects information on basic human values. The ultimate goal is to provide insights into the ideas, beliefs, preferences, attitudes, values and opinions of citizens all over Europe. The survey is repeated every nine years. In turn, the WVS is a representative comparative social survey, conducted globally every five years, that aims to assess the impact of values on the social, political and economic development of societies.

Following Kleven (2022), we construct an index of gender norms (*GNI*) based on the average standardized response to questions related to women's position in the labour market. Since our focus is on parental labour market decisions, this indicator reflects individual beliefs about women's participation in the workforce. Importantly, and given the likelihood of endogeneity — gender norms influencing parental labour market trajectories and, at the same time, labour market decisions shaping attitudes and beliefs —, studying the impact of gender norms on women's and men's employment decisions may encounter problems of reverse causality. To address this concern, we focus on the beliefs of women in the same age range as the mothers of our economic agents, whom we define from here on as “grandmothers” and assume a considerable degree of intergenerational transmission of gender norms (Farré and Vella, 2013).

We establish two cohorts of grandmothers, a , and two cohorts of mothers, $a - 28$. Thus, for the mothers aged 20 to 29, the corresponding grandmothers are aged 48 to 57. For the mothers aged 30 to 39, the corresponding grandmothers are aged 58 to 67. Note that we take 28 years of age as the reference because it is the mean age of women at birth of their first child during the whole period for all countries that we consider. Furthermore, since we consider the beliefs

of older cohorts of women (the “grandmothers”), including immigrants could introduce considerable measurement error because these women may rather be influenced by the gender norms prevalent in their region of origin rather than the region of residence (Alesina and Giuliano, 2015; Giuliano, 2021). By restricting the analysis to natives, we aim to minimize this potential bias and enhance the accuracy of our assessment of gender norms’ impact on parents’ employment decisions.

The *GNI* is constructed for each grandmothers cohort, time period, and importantly, region. This way we take into account the variability that there may be across regions within the same country and it allows us to work with a larger number of units.² Specifically, we use four questions that ask respondents their level of agreement with the following statements:

- When jobs are scarce, men have more right to a job than women.
- A pre-school child is likely to suffer if his or her mother works.
- A job is alright, but what most women really want is a home and children.
- Being a housewife is just as fulfilling as working for pay.

First, we code the responses to each question such that a higher value indicates stronger gender progressivity. Then, we normalize the responses to be between zero and one given that all four questions are indexed in different ways.³ After that first normalization, the responses are standardized to have mean zero and standard deviation one.⁴ Next, we collapse the data at the cohort, region, and year level to have the average of the responses within each cell. However, some region-interval combinations have missing values for the *GNI* due to incomplete survey coverage. In such cases, we proceed to impute these missing values using a percentile-based method that preserves each region’s relative standing over time following the work by Kleven (2022). Specifically, for each year, we calculate the percentile rank of each region’s observed index value, indicating how a region compares to others within that year. Then, we compute the average percentile for each region across all years in which the index is observed. This represents the region’s relative position over time. Lastly, for each region-interval combination with missing *GNI*, we impute the missing value by applying the region’s average percentile to the distribution of observed index values within the same year. This ensures that the imputed value reflects the region’s usual rank, adjusted to the context of that specific year. At the end, we end up with 190 regions from 31 different countries observed in 15 different years.⁵

Next, we merge the *GNI* at the cohort, region, and year level with the LFS sample which has information at the individual level. Within the EU-LFS sample, we consider 11 labour market outcomes: the probability of (1) working; (2) being in part-time work; (3) being self-employed; (4) having a fixed-term contract; (5) acting as a supervisor in a firm; (6) working in the public sector; (7) working during the weekends; (8) working usually from home; (9) working in more than one job; (10) being an underemployed part-time worker; and, (11) working in a high-skill

² We take the most disaggregated form of NUTS possible. For most countries, the information we have is at NUTS-II level. However, for some of them, we only have the information at NUTS-I level. We had to go through an intensive work of homogenizing the regions across years and across datasets in order to obtain a longitudinal dataset at regional level.

³ The first question has three different categories (‘agree’, ‘neither’, ‘disagree’), whereas the rest have four (‘strongly agree’, ‘agree’, ‘disagree’, ‘strongly disagree’).

⁴ In addition, we also construct an index solely normalized, and an index solely standardized. The results, available from the authors upon request, remain consistent regardless of which index we use.

⁵ Table A.1 provides all the detail regarding the regions that needed to be imputed by year.

occupation. Section A.1 in the Appendix provides the definitions for all variables. We augment our database with additional regional variables obtained from Eurostat: the unemployment rate, the fertility rate, the total population in the region, and the share of population with tertiary education.

Table 1 provides summary statistics for all these labour market outcomes as well as the individual and regional controls. The first column refers to mothers, the second column to childless women, the third column to fathers and the fourth column to childless men. As noted in the 'Introduction', and shown in Panel A, women are, in general, less likely to work than men, but within females, childless women are more likely to work while, within males, childless men are less likely to work compared to fathers. The pattern reverses regarding part-time work: mothers are more likely to work part-time than childless women while the same is true for childless men compared to fathers. As a matter of fact, mothers are ten times more likely to work part-time than fathers. Men are more likely to be self-employed than women, particularly fathers. Having a child is associated with a smaller likelihood of holding a fixed-term contract both for women and men. Fathers are the most likely to be supervisors in their workplace. Differences are not very large across columns when it comes to the probability of working during the weekend, working from home or holding multiple jobs. Mothers are the least likely to be underemployed with fathers being the most likely. Lastly, women are more likely to be in an occupation that requires high skills compared to men, particularly, to childless men.

As for the individual controls, shown in Panel B, our results indicate that mothers and fathers are older than childless individuals, they also have more education (particularly compared to childless women), and are much more likely to live with a partner, though such likelihood is not as high among mothers than among fathers. Regarding regional controls, as expected, results are very similar across columns provided that the distribution of the four demographic groups is not very different across European regions — see Panel C of Table 1.

Finally, and when it comes to the *GNI*, Panel D of Table 1 shows that childless individuals hold more progressive gender norms, particularly among females. Mothers and fathers are, in comparison, more conservative.

Table 1: Summary statistics

	Women		Men	
	Mothers (1)	Childless (2)	Fathers (3)	Childless (4)
Panel A: Labour market outcome variables				
Working	0.601 (0.490)	0.676 (0.468)	0.912 (0.283)	0.725 (0.447)
Part-time	0.343 (0.475)	0.194 (0.396)	0.037 (0.188)	0.086 (0.280)
Self-employed	0.092 (0.289)	0.065 (0.246)	0.177 (0.382)	0.122 (0.328)
Fixed-term	0.126 (0.332)	0.222 (0.416)	0.092 (0.289)	0.184 (0.387)
Supervisor	0.163 (0.370)	0.157 (0.364)	0.268 (0.443)	0.181 (0.385)
Weekends	0.221 (0.415)	0.261 (0.439)	0.261 (0.439)	0.257 (0.437)
Telework	0.062 (0.241)	0.046 (0.210)	0.049 (0.216)	0.043 (0.202)
Multiple jobs	0.029 (0.168)	0.042 (0.200)	0.039 (0.195)	0.036 (0.186)
Underemployment	0.099 (0.299)	0.239 (0.427)	0.299 (0.458)	0.283 (0.451)
Public sector	0.369 (0.483)	0.331 (0.471)	0.146 (0.353)	0.135 (0.342)
High skill	0.482 (0.500)	0.481 (0.500)	0.384 (0.486)	0.358 (0.479)
Panel B: Individual controls				
Age	31.815 (4.583)	27.731 (5.459)	33.273 (4.051)	28.405 (5.476)
Low education	0.180 (0.384)	0.101 (0.302)	0.201 (0.401)	0.170 (0.375)
Medium education	0.480 (0.500)	0.521 (0.500)	0.519 (0.500)	0.581 (0.493)
High education	0.340 (0.474)	0.377 (0.485)	0.281 (0.449)	0.250 (0.433)
Living with partner	0.886 (0.318)	0.342 (0.475)	0.985 (0.121)	0.251 (0.433)
Panel C: Regional controls				
Population	3.816 (4.181)	3.729 (4.123)	3.809 (4.216)	3.634 (4.050)
Fertility rate	1.536 (0.239)	1.535 (0.239)	1.537 (0.238)	1.527 (0.235)
Share of tertiary educated	25.354 (9.689)	26.489 (10.485)	25.248 (9.718)	25.937 (10.336)
Unemployment rate	8.391 (4.410)	8.297 (4.460)	8.345 (4.346)	8.343 (4.491)
Panel D: Gender norms				
Gender norm index	-0.158 (0.464)	-0.048 (0.517)	-0.175 (0.467)	-0.079 (0.512)
Number of observations	1524873	2787254	1148962	3607114

Note: The sample includes native men and women aged 20-39. The table includes only fathers and mothers of children who are five years of age or younger. All the labour market outcome variables, except Working, are conditional on being employed. Due to missing data, the number of observations varies across variables. The reported number of observations reflects the total number of individuals in each group. Population is reported in millions.

Source: Authors' calculations based on data from the EU-LFS (2000–2022) and the Integrated Values Survey (2000–2022).

Figure 2 plots the evolution of the gender norms index over decade intervals for the two cohorts of grandmothers. We can observe a steady, upward tendency, indicating that, over time, gender norms have become more egalitarian, with the youngest cohort consistently scoring higher (more progressive) than the older cohort at each decade.

Figure 2: Evolution of the gender norm index by cohort

Note: The index has been first normalized to take values between zero and one, and then standardized to have mean zero and standard deviation one.

Source: Authors' computation, using data from the Integrated Values Survey (2000-2022).

Figure 3 shows a strong, positive relationship between the two grandmothers' cohort average gender-norm scores across all regions. All points cluster tightly around the 45° line, indicating that areas where the older cohort hold more egalitarian views generally do so among the younger cohort, and vice-versa. Nordic regions show more progressive beliefs, whereas Central-Eastern European regions hold more traditional beliefs. Anglo- Saxon and Continental regions fall in the middle, and the Mediterranean regions exhibit the highest dispersion. The departures of some Mediterranean and Continental points from the diagonal suggest that in a few regions the youngest adults have moved ahead (or lagged behind) compared to their elders in adopting less traditional norms. The figure underscores that while deeply ingrained regional cultures

shape gender attitudes across generations, there is modest but meaningful variation in how quickly different regions' younger cohorts are shifting toward more egalitarian views.

Figure 3: Regional comparison of gender norms index by cohort

Note: The values plotted are region-decade averages over the whole period of analysis. Countries are classified into five groups, based on geographical location: Continental Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Switzerland), Anglo-Saxon countries (Iceland, Ireland, UK), Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Norway, Sweden), Central-Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia), and Mediterranean countries (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Spain)

Source: Authors' computation, using data from the Integrated Values Survey (2000–2022).

Finally, Figure 4 shows that the intergenerational transmission of gender norms is a reality in European regions. The correlation between the gender norms index for mothers compared to that of grandmothers is very high with most points closely clustered to the 45° line. The same is true for the correlation between the gender norms held by fathers with that of grandmothers.

Figure 4: Correlation with grandmothers' gender norm indexes

Note: The index has been first normalized to take values between zero and one, and then standardized to have mean zero and standard deviation one.

Source: Authors' computation, using data from the Integrated Values Survey (2000-2022).

4. Identification strategy

Following Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas (2021), we exploit the across cohort and over time variation within regions to estimate the effect of progressive gender norms on mothers and fathers' labour market decisions relative to their childless counterparts. Formally, we estimate the following specification:

$$Y_{icrt}^{a-28} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GNI_{crt}^a + \alpha_2 Child_{icrt}^{a-28} + \alpha_3 (GNI_{crt}^a * Child_{icrt}^{a-28}) + X_{icrt}^{a-28'} \gamma + Z'_{crt} + \phi_r + \rho_{ct} + \epsilon_{icrt}^{a-28}$$

where Y_{icrt}^{a-28} is equal to 1 if individual l from birth cohort $a - 28$, living in region r of country c is, for example, working in survey year t , and 0 if the individual is not working. GNI_{crt}^a is the index of gender norms of, for instance, women in cohort a , region r of country c , and survey year t . $Child_{icrt}^{a-28}$ is equal to 1 if individual l from birth cohort $a - 28$, living in region r of country c , has a child 0 to 5 years old in the survey year t , and equal to 0 if the individual is childless. $X_{icrt}^{a-28'}$ is a vector of individual-specific covariates measured at survey year t , namely age, age squared, education dummies, and an indicator for whether the person is living with a partner. Z'_{crt} is a set of regional/year covariates measured contemporaneously, namely the unemployment rate, the fertility rate, the total population in the region, and the share of tertiary educated individuals in the population. ϕ_r captures region fixed effects, and ρ_{ct} captures country-by-year fixed effects.

To address the potential endogeneity between labour market decisions and gender norms, we undertake an instrumental variable approach. We construct an instrument that considers the percentage of highly religious people in each region and year. Multiple studies have established a strong relationship between religiosity and traditional gender norms. In a recent meta-analysis, Sobiecki and Kosakowska-Berezecka (2025) show that religiosity is positively associated

with both forms of ambivalent sexism: hostile and benevolent. The link is particularly strong in the case of benevolent sexism which reflects positive yet patronizing attitudes that reinforce traditional gender roles, undermine women's autonomy, and negatively affect personal and professional achievements (Glick and Fiske, 2001). Guiso et al. (2003) show that religious people tend to be less favourable with respect to working women, while Heineck (2004) documents that women who participate regularly in religious activities are less inclined towards paid employment. Following the Pew Research Center (2014) "Religious Landscape Study"⁶ in the US, we combine the answers to four questions related to religion and construct an index that captures each individual's level of religiosity. In particular, we use the answers to the following questions:

- How important is religion in your life?
- Apart from weddings, funerals and christenings, about how often do you attend religious services these days?
- How often do you pray to God outside of religious services?
- How important is God in your life?

Each individual is assigned a score of 1, 0, or -1 on each measure based on their level of religious observance, which is categorized as high, medium, or low, respectively. High religious observance is defined as answering that religion is very important, attending religious services at least once a month, praying daily, and indicating that God is very important in their life. Medium religious observance is characterized by stating that religion is somewhat important, attending services on special holy days or annually, praying more than a few times per year, and considering God somewhat important. Low religiosity is defined as indicating that religion is not very or not at all important, rarely or never attending services, rarely or never praying, and stating that God is not important at all.⁷ The scores for each measure are then summed, and individuals are classified into three categories based on their total score: those with a score of -2 or lower are classified as "not religious", those with a score between -1 and 1 as "moderately religious" and those with a score of 2 or higher as "highly religious". Our instrument is defined as the percentage of highly religious people in each region and year. As in the previous section, those region-year combinations with missing data on the prevalence of highly religious people, the percentage has been imputed following the methodology proposed by Kleven (2022).

Figure 5 reveals a clear, generational decline in the share of "highly religious" individuals from 1990 to 2020. In 1990, about 40% of 48-57-year-olds and roughly 55% of 58-67-year-olds reported high religiosity. Both cohorts exhibit a steady downward trend through 2000 and 2010, with the younger cohort falling to 31% and the older to 37%. After 2010 the drop accelerates: by 2020 only about 12% of the youngest group and 22% of the older group remain highly religious. Throughout the period, the older cohort remains more religious than the younger cohort, but the gap narrows, indicating both that religiosity is declining and that relatively younger adults are secularizing more rapidly than older adults.

⁶ <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2016/02/29/how-religious-is-your-state/?state=alabama>

⁷ The question regarding God's importance in one's life is measured on a scale from 1 to 10, with 1 being not at all important and 10 being very important. We recoded this variable so that responses of 3 or below are categorized as "religion is not important at all", 4 to 7 as "somewhat important" and 8 or above as "very important".

Figure 5: Evolution of the percentage of highly religious people by cohort

Source: Authors' computation, using data from the Integrated Values Survey (2000-2022).

Finally, we are confident on our instrumental variable strategy because the first stage regression in which the gender norm index is regressed against the percentage of highly religious individuals in the region by year yields a negative coefficient statistically significant at 99% indicating that there is a clear negative association between the percentage of highly religious people and progressive gender norms. Moreover, the F-statistic of this regression is 21.01 and therefore well above the rule of thumb of 10.

5. Results

Table 2 shows the results of the IV specification for all the labour market outcomes under analysis.⁸ Panel A shows the results for women, whereas Panel B presents those of men. All coefficients in the table already account for the potential endogeneity of non-traditional gender norms and labour market decisions. Recall that our coefficient of interest in Equation (1) is α_3 for the interaction between having a child and the gender norms index.

The first column indicates that exposure to non-traditional gender norms is associated with a lower probability of working for fathers while the coefficient for mothers does not attain statistical significance at 95% confidence level. Possibly, the mechanism behind these results is the fact that fathers in more progressive regions take a larger share of care and family

⁸ Table A.2 in the Appendix shows the results of the reduced form regressions.

responsibilities than in more traditional areas and therefore are more likely to be out of the labour market. Unlike Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas (2021), we do not find that living in an area where previous generations hold more progressive gender norms increases the likelihood for mothers of being employed.

Column (2) shows the results relative to the likelihood for parents to work part-time. While one could have expected that exposure to non-traditional norms reduces the probability for mothers to work few hours a week and mostly have full-time jobs, results indicate that this is not the case. As a matter of fact, mothers in more progressive regions are more likely to work part-time according to our results. We hypothesize that perhaps the alternative for these mothers would be not working at all given they care for a child less than 6 years of age and therefore more progressive gender norms actually help them to enter the labour market even if it is in a part-time basis. On the contrary, results indicate that fathers in less traditional areas are less likely to work part-time. Thus, having a child in more progressive regions affects fathers' extensive margin and (slightly) also their intensive margin.

Furthermore, columns (3) to (5) consider the likelihood of working during the weekends, being self-employed and holding a fixed-term contract. Results indicate that gender norms have little influence on these labour market outcomes neither for mothers nor for fathers. All the coefficients of interest are negative but none of them is statistically significant at 95%. Column (6) shows the potential correlation between non-traditional gender norms and having reached a supervisor role in the firm where one works. Both coefficients are positive but only for fathers is statistically meaningful. Thus, progressive gender norms somewhat help fathers to pursue a supervisor position in their workplace.

Column (7) documents that progressive gender norms are associated with a higher likelihood of remote work for both, mothers and fathers. Such finding likely indicates that the more non-traditional the region where one lives is, the more likely parents are to take the flexibility that certain jobs allow. Columns (8) to (10) which account for holding multiple jobs, underemployment and working in the public sector indicate that gender norms do not exert any influence in the probability of such type of outcome in the case of mothers. Instead, all these job characteristics are negatively associated with progressive gender norms in the case of fathers. This means that living in a more progressive region precludes fathers from holding multiple jobs, being underemployed or working in the public sector. Considering the other side of the coin, it would mean that fathers in traditional regions are more likely to take certain disadvantages in the labour market.

Lastly, column (11) indicates that gender norms, once again, do not exert any influence in the likelihood for mothers to hold a high-skill job but do increase the probability for fathers to do so. Progressive gender norms seem to help fathers to look for more advantageous positions in the labour market.

Table 2: IV regressions

Panel A: Mothers vs. Childless women											
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
	Working	Part-time	Weekends	Self-employment	Fixed-term	Supervisor	Teleworking	Multiple-job	Underemployment	Public sector	High-skill job
<i>GNI</i> x Child	-0.0328*	0.1259***	-0.0023	-0.0045	-0.0181*	0.0018	0.0110***	-0.0100*	0.0345	0.0085*	-0.0036
	(0.0163)	(0.0326)	(0.0049)	(0.0036)	(0.0073)	(0.0043)	(0.0028)	(0.0039)	(0.0322)	(0.0037)	(0.0041)
<i>GNI</i>	0.0220	-0.0496**	-0.0098	-0.0169	0.0209	0.0040	-0.0256**	-0.0025	-0.0142	0.0003	-0.0045
	(0.0130)	(0.0177)	(0.0170)	(0.0086)	(0.0177)	(0.0150)	(0.0096)	(0.0043)	(0.0276)	(0.0164)	(0.0185)
Child	-0.2034***	0.2054***	-0.0297***	0.0076***	-0.0067*	-0.0291***	0.0056***	-0.0079***	-0.1085***	0.0357***	-0.0229***
	(0.0123)	(0.0215)	(0.0034)	(0.0015)	(0.0032)	(0.0043)	(0.0015)	(0.0009)	(0.0145)	(0.0027)	(0.0031)
Observations	4006489	2611657	2282572	2612200	2373449	2056786	2467336	2607982	626782	2576569	2582113
Panel B: Fathers vs. Childless men											
<i>GNI</i> x Child	-0.0454***	-0.0186**	-0.0097*	-0.0075	-0.0143	0.0273***	0.0083***	-0.0085**	-0.0438**	-0.0116***	0.0200***
	(0.0113)	(0.0069)	(0.0043)	(0.0046)	(0.0077)	(0.0051)	(0.0017)	(0.0028)	(0.0142)	(0.0023)	(0.0058)
<i>GNI</i>	0.0248	-0.0100	-0.0196	-0.0129	0.0351*	-0.0144	-0.0201*	-0.0099	0.0030	0.0045	-0.0120
	(0.0133)	(0.0080)	(0.0196)	(0.0121)	(0.0136)	(0.0142)	(0.0088)	(0.0059)	(0.0475)	(0.0103)	(0.0120)
Child	-0.0002	0.0020	0.0041*	0.0184***	-0.0099***	0.0214***	0.0003	0.0020*	-0.0204***	-0.0016	-0.0198***
	(0.0031)	(0.0030)	(0.0018)	(0.0020)	(0.0025)	(0.0023)	(0.0008)	(0.0008)	(0.0061)	(0.0013)	(0.0019)
Observations	4413845	3429178	3033045	3430309	2906576	2509963	3258673	3424136	240476	3384621	3390937

Note: Regressions include a set of individual and regional controls. Individual controls include age, education, and whether the individual lives with a partner (our proxy for marital status). Regional controls include fertility rate, population, unemployment rate, and the share of individuals with tertiary education. All regressions also include region and country by year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the regional level.

Source: Authors' calculations based on data from the EU-LFS (2000–2022) and the Integrated Values Survey (2000–2022).

6. Conclusions

This paper studies to which extent gender norms exert an influence on the type of labour market attachment that mothers and fathers have across 31 European countries. This way, we move beyond the mere analysis of the influence of social norms on the binary decision of participating in the labour market, but we look at 10 other job characteristics that also shape the labour market trajectories of parents of young children. Unlike most previous analyses, we focus on both mothers and fathers to learn if future changes in social norms can help reduce gender inequalities in the labour market and contribute to a more equal division of work and care. We use an instrumental variable approach on individual-level data from the EU-LFS and cohort-level data from the IVS for more than two decades.

Our results indicate that gender norms have more influence on the job characteristics that fathers hold than on those that mothers have. While, for mothers, more progressive gender norms are linked with only two of the 11 outcomes under analysis (part-time and remote work); for fathers, the impact is not only on the likelihood of being employed (negatively) but also on seven other outcomes. This way, more progressive gender norms are negatively associated with part-time work, holding multiple jobs, underemployment and being in the public sector whereas they are positively associated with being a supervisor, teleworking or having a high-skill job.

Taken together, results indicate that the progressivity of gender norms seems to help mothers to take advantage of job characteristics that provide them with flexibility in the labour market, possibly with the ultimate goal of balancing work and childcare responsibilities. In the case of fathers, it somewhat seems as if non-traditional gender norms help them avoid disadvantage in the labour market (as having to hold multiple jobs or underemployment) while providing them with certain advantages (as being a supervisor or holding a high-skill job). Future studies should focus on better understanding the mechanisms behind our findings which, at the same time, could provide clues as how more progressive gender norms could also help women to hold more advantageous positions in the labour market.

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A Appendix

A.1 Variables definitions

Employed: those 15 to 89 who, during the reference week, i) worked for at least one hour for pay or profit, including those working as family workers, or ii) were absent from work but had an attachment to their job due to holidays, working time arrangements, sick leave, maternity or paternity leave, job-related training, parental leave and receiving job-related income, seasonal workers that continue to perform some task of the job, or for any other reason for a total duration of 3 months or less.

Part time: people in employment declaring working part-time in the main job, based on their own perception referring to the usual hours worked.

Self-employment: people working in their own business, professional practice or farm for the purpose of earning a profit derived from the goods or services produced, either with or without employees.

Fixed-term contract: employees working in jobs that will terminate wither after a period of time determined in advanced, or after a period not known in advanced but defined by objective criteria, such as the completion of an assignment or the period of absence of an employee temporarily replaced.

Supervisor: employees that formally supervises –i.e., takes care of the work of other employees, directs their work, and sees that is satisfactorily carried out– the work of at least one other person.

Public sector: people in employment who work in the public sector, approximated by the aggregation of the O (Public Administration and Defence; Compulsory Social Security), P (Education) and Q (Health and Social Work) sectors of the NACE classification (Rubery, 2013; Campos et al., 2017).

Weekends: people in employment who frequently (at least two Saturdays or Sundays per month) works on Saturdays or Sundays within a reference period of four to twelve working weeks preceding the end of the reference week.

Teleworking: people in employment who mainly (at least half of the time) do any productive work related to their current main job at home in a reference period of four to twelve working weeks preceding the end of the reference week.

Multiple jobs: people in employment who report working in more than one job in the reference week.

Underemployment: people in employment who, during the reference week, i) are working part time, ii) wish to work additional hours, and iii) are available to do so.

High skill occupations: people in employment who work as managers, professionals, or technicians and associate professionals.

A.2 Additional tables and figures

Table A.1: Imputed region-year GNI

Year	Imputed Regions
1999	CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, DEF, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL62, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, IE01, IE02, ITF5, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, SE21, SE31, SE32, UKC
2000	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES22, ES23, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2005	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITF5, ITF6, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04

Continued on next page

Table A.1 (Continued)

Year	Imputed Regions
2006	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE5, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR7, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2007	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES24, ES43, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2008	BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, ES23, ES62, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2009	AT1, AT2, AT3, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, IE01, IE02, ITC2, ITH, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04

Continued on next page

Table A.1 (Continued)

Year	Imputed Regions
2011	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES23, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2012	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2013	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE9, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM

Continued on next page

Table A.1 (Continued)

Year	Imputed Regions
2017	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, CY00, EE00, ES13, ES23, ES43, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, UKC, UKD, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2018	BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, HR03, HR04, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC2, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04
2019	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SI03, SI04, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM

Continued on next page

Table A.1 (Continued)

Year	Imputed Regions
2020	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SIO3, SIO4, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM
2021	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, CZ01, CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ078, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, MT00, NL00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SIO3, SIO4, SK01, SK02, SK03, SK04, UKC, UKD, UKE, UKF, UKG, UKH, UKIJ, UKK, UKL, UKM

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Table A.1 (Continued)

Year	Imputed Regions
2022	AT1, AT2, AT3, BE10, BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35, BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG41, BG42, CH01, CH02, CH03, CH04, CH05, CH06, CH07, CY00, DE1, DE2, DE3, DE4, DE5, DE6, DE7, DE8, DE9, DEA, DEB, DEC, DED, DEE, DEF, DEG, DK01, DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05, EE00, EL30, EL40, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65, ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70, FI19, FI1BC, FI1D, FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5, FR6, FR7, FR8, HR03, HR04, HU10, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33, IE01, IE02, IS00, ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4, LT00, LU00, LV00, MT00, NO02, NO06, NO07, NO0A0809, PL21, PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63, PL71, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL9, PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, RO11, RO12, RO21, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42, SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33, SI03, SI04

Note: The table lists all NUTS-2 regions for which the Gender Norms Index (*GNI*) was imputed in each year. Imputation was performed for region-year cells where the index could not be directly computed due to missing survey data. Values were imputed based on each region's historical percentile distribution relative to other regions within the same time interval.

Source: Author's computation, using data from the IV

Table A.2: Reduced form regressions (year)

Panel A: Mothers vs. Childless women											
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
	Working	Part-time	Weekends	Self-employment	Fixed-term	Supervisor	Teleworking	Multiple-job	Underemployment	Public sector	High-skill job
Highly religiosity	0.2790*** (0.0334)	0.0480 (0.0303)	-0.1391*** (0.0141)	0.0852*** (0.0085)	-0.3162*** (0.0297)	0.1413*** (0.0135)	0.0562*** (0.0084)	0.0024 (0.0036)	-0.1565*** (0.0196)	0.1563*** (0.0137)	0.2262*** (0.0232)
Observations	4047354	2619272	2289332	2619781	2378406	2061037	2474540	2615533	629157	2580507	2587186
Panel B: Fathers vs. Childless men											
Highly religiosity	0.4041*** (0.0425)	-0.0970*** (0.0136)	-0.0064 (0.0084)	0.1676*** (0.0161)	-0.2719*** (0.0277)	0.2403*** (0.0259)	0.0435*** (0.0062)	0.0203*** (0.0034)	0.0419* (0.0187)	0.0706*** (0.0075)	0.2095*** (0.0216)
Observations	4465487	3438552	3041186	3439627	2912464	2514794	3267461	3433451	241576	3389725	3397388

Note: Regressions include a set of individual and regional controls. Individual controls include age, education, and whether the individual lives with a partner (our proxy for marital status). Regional controls include fertility rate, population, unemployment rate, and the share of individuals with tertiary education. All regressions also include region and country by year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the regional level.

Source: Authors' calculations based on data from the EU-LFS (2000–2022) and the Integrated Values Survey (2000–2022).

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